

PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF INCREASING STUDENT MOVEMENT ACTIVITY (ON THE EXAMPLE OF WRESTLING AND MOVING GAMES)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6629298>

Annotation. *The article provides information on the use of wrestling in the development of agility in students, the introduction of a set of agility to improve the effectiveness of their technical and tactical movements, the importance of agility exercises in improving technical and tactical movements.*

Keywords: *wrestling, agility quality, agility exercise set, technical-tactical actions, coordination capabilities.*

INTRODUCTION

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On measures to further improve the management system in the field of culture and sports" marked a new era in the development of sports in our country. According to the decree, the State Committee for Physical Culture and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established. Involvement of the general population in sports, upbringing of a physically healthy generation, development of sports industry and infrastructure, holding of mass sports events and competitions in cities and districts, selection, training and skills of talented athletes in cooperation with the National Olympic Committee, sports federations and associations, training, introduction of modern technologies in the field and expansion of international relations were identified as its main tasks [1].

Wrestling is a sport in which two athletes compete one-on-one in accordance with the established rules. The art of wrestling has been known in many nations since ancient times. Wrestling is especially popular in Greece and has been a regular feature of the ancient Olympic Games. Various forms of national wrestling exist in Greece, Italy, Japan, Turkey, Iran, Afghanistan, Russia, Uzbekistan, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and other countries.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In our country, J.M. Nurshin, R.S. Salamov, F.A.Kerimov, T.C. Usmonxo'jaev, A.Sh. Abdullaev, Sh.X. In the researches of Khankeldievs the forms and methods of enrichment of educational content of physical education lessons are dissolved F.A. Kerimov, N.M. Yusupov, Sh.A, Abdullaev, R.D. Xalmuxamedov, V.N. Shin, G.B. Abdurasulova, S.C.Tajibaev, J.M. Nurshin, Sh.A. The scientific works of Mirzakulov, AR Taymuratov, NA Tastanov, ZS Artikov reflect the history, organizational basis and methodology of individual wrestling. A.Atoev, J.Nurshin, R.Salomov, F.Kerimov, O.Toymurodov, J.Tashpulatov, H.Bobobekov, M.Sodikov, N.Azizov, H.Akhmedov developed methodological bases. He conducted research on the history, organizational foundations and methods of individual wrestling, the use of movement games in the training process, the development of physical qualities.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Recently, the term "technical and tactical skills" is widely used in the practice of wrestling. Wrestling techniques, in the narrow sense, are the most sensible methods of

performing actions that bring victory to the wrestler. At the same time, the basis of the technique is actions based on the biomechanical and physiological laws inherent in all of them, regardless of the individual characteristics of the wrestlers. Tactics in sports means the forms and methods of achieving high results, as well as all the methods and forms of winning over the opponent.

In martial arts, especially wrestling, the technique and tactics are so closely intertwined that in order to differentiate the movements of the wrestler, some experts differ on which movements are technical and which are tactical. In fact, they form a dialectical unity.

At the beginning of the development of the sport of wrestling, rules were created to determine the technical and tactical actions, depending on the technique used by wrestlers. This is how different types of wrestling came into being. These rules were later changed separately for the types of wrestling. With their help, attempts were made to limit some actions and encourage others. Depending on the number and quality of technical and tactical movements used, attempts were made to change the rules in such a way that these changes improved the sporting and spectacular characteristics of the wrestling.

In the process of physical education, along with the skills of proper shaping, self-management, adherence to the agenda and hygienic requirements, the struggle for the formation of mental, moral, spiritual, aesthetic, volitional qualities of the student's health and physical development is more effective than sports. need to use.

The high level of positive impact of physical activity and physical exercises performed by students on the development of the student's body in wrestling lessons and their effective implementation depends on the practical knowledge and professional skills of the teacher.

In the process of wrestling with students, it is important to perform general developmental exercises, to ensure proper breathing and methodologically correct organization of the exercises and their proper execution.

The compliance of the place of wrestling training with sanitary and hygienic requirements, the suitability of students' sportswear and footwear for the purpose of training, is an important tool for the elimination of medical, physical defects and shortcomings in the physical development of students. Failure to ensure that the classroom meets the hygienic requirements of the classroom and the students can have a negative impact on the proper formation of the supporting limbs and posture of the students, as well as their physical development.

Teaching students age-appropriate movements, including the names and rules of national games, and the ability to actively participate in them, such as running and jumping, age-appropriate standards, cleansing, agility, and exercise to ensure the physical development of preschoolers. is the basis of educational content.

Age, gender, personal-mental and physiological characteristics of students should be taken into account in the organization of wrestling lessons.

Research in the field of sports morphology has shown that wrestlers with certain general dimensions and body proportions are more likely to use certain techniques. For example, the longer the wrist, the greater the relative forces of the flexor and extensor muscles. The longer the hip and leg, the greater the absolute forces of the flexor and extensor muscles of the hip, and the less the relative forces.

Accordingly, it is likely that wrestlers with shorter arms and legs will perform the lifts much more easily, because in this case the effectiveness of the work depends on the relative strength. For wrestlers with long arms and legs, it is more convenient to use methods related to the movements performed without breaking the opponent from the carpet, using the conditions of unstable balance (favorable dynamic situation). In addition, the long arms and legs provide swallowing from the road and speed. At the same time, the technical and tactical capabilities also depend on the specific individual characteristics of the strength training. Therefore, the technical movements associated with tearing an opponent off the mat have relatively well-developed recumbent shoulder muscles and can be performed relatively lightly by relatively tall wrestlers.

To date, there is no consensus on the minimum level of technical-tactical offensive action that a highly skilled fighter should have. Famous wrestlers have mastered and successfully used a "royal" method that suits them. Some wrestlers have developed about 30 moves that end in a single method. At the same time, famous wrestlers began to appear, who had several options for the successful completion of the attack. Such wrestlers were usually rewarded for the best technique in competitions. Due to the intensity of competition in major competitions, highly qualified wrestlers have expanded their tactical capabilities while maintaining the "royal" methods in their technical and tactical movements. Some wrestlers have mastered two and sometimes three "royal" methods.

Research on modern wrestling techniques shows that famous wrestlers use 16-20 variants of various technical and tactical offensive movements during a competition. In addition, the strongest fighters attack effectively and reliably enough. Only when the attack is tactically well prepared do they use maximum power and speed. By using tactical movements that do not require large voltages, they save energy and maintain performance until the end of the competition. More than 50% of offensive actions are judged by the competition judges as an advantage.

The tutor should constantly monitor the students' regular adherence to the daily routine and hygienic requirements, proper nutrition in a timely manner, the correct organization of morning physical education classes.

Information about the origin and history of the games has come down to us through the book "Devonulug'otitturk" by Mahmud Kashgari, the great millennial, historian and ethnographer of the XI century. The play contains examples of game forms, such as summoning, gathering, starting the game, checking, which are carried out before the start of the Uzbek action games.

To do this, the actions in the game must be appropriate to the student's ability to control himself; these movements should be pre-mastered in systemic exercises.

Regular movement games help students develop control of their movements, they regulate their body, that is, they are taught to move at different tensions.

Games allow the reader to move with great agility, specific purpose, and speed; teaches to follow rules, to behave, to value friendship.

The first-year students were brought up in families with the help of puzzles, fun games related to the first movement of the student. In the lives of students older than him, folk games with a variety of action content (including game beginnings, rhymes, countdowns, which captivate students) have played an important role.

Moving games are a basic tool of physical education. Moving games have a creative effect on the physical development of students' motor activity, the formation of motor skills and physical qualities, strengthening health by increasing the functional activity of the body and enhancing feelings of emotional joy.

The healing effect achieved by conducting active games is inextricably linked with the positive emotions that occur in the course of students' play activities and have a positive effect on the student's psyche.

Emotional upliftment awakens in students a desire to achieve a goal that is common to all, and it is necessary to have a clear understanding of the tasks, the coherence of actions, a clear goal in space and game conditions, to complete tasks quickly.

The role of the will, which helps students overcome various obstacles, is enhanced based on their strong passion and enjoyable aspiration to achieve the goal. Motion games serve as a method of improving the motor skills and physical qualities previously acquired by students.

During the game, the student focuses on achieving the goal, not on the way the action is performed. He acts in accordance with the conditions of the game, showing agility and improving his movements.

CONCLUSION

As a movement activity, wrestling sprtt type and action game has certain peculiarities: it requires the reader to respond quickly to signals and sudden changes in the game. Almost every action game has action and student movement signals. For example, "sparrows and cars", "airplanes". Active movement activity in the game exercises the student's nervous system, improving the processes of excitation and braking, develops observation, resourcefulness, the ability to target in the environment, courage, agility, initiative, independent choice of goal. Wrestling and movement games as the main tool in the system of physical culture and sports, along with the use of various exercises in sports, the widespread use of movement games, first of all, helps young people to grow up physically and mentally healthy. serves as one of the main tools.

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